

Systematic Literature Analysis for Supply Chain Conflicts: Paving the Way for Future Studies

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Abstract

This research provides a systematic overview regarding the Supply Chain Conflicts in Business-to-Business (B2B) relationships and defines and categorizes the main conflict areas and resolution mechanisms by conducting a content analysis. Based on the screening of 343 studies published mainly in the literature on marketing, business, management literature and other disciplines during 2010-2021, a systematic review and a content analysis were applied to find out the current situation and future research directions on this topic. In this research, within the context of descriptive analysis, sectoral-based analysis enables us to identify areas where conflicts are prevalent and where there is a need for further action. Regarding content analysis, highly fragmented synthesis presents how areas of conflicts and conflict resolution mechanisms are formed in the current B2B context. By providing a summary of the existing research direction on the subject, published in peer-reviewed international journals that publish research in English, this study contributes to the future academic work by identifying conflict sources and resolution methods to achieve better conflict management practices within the supply chains. With the findings of the research, companies can review their business practices and the underlying factors of conflict situations to improve their supply chains and gain ideas for their resolution. This research also contributes to the industrial marketing literature by providing an assembled and synthesized knowledge for scholars on supply chain conflicts with resolution mechanisms in both the social sciences and interdisciplinary management; deriving a comprehensive analysis of methods and insights addressed by researchers in the field.

Key words: Supply Chain Conflict, SLR, B2B Relationships, Conflict Resolution, Content Analysis

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1. Introduction

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Whenever people or companies work together, conflict is inevitable (Daft, 1997), and it has been the subject of many disciplines including psychology, sociology, business, management, and marketing for years. In supply chains, channel conflict arises within the channel when a channel member perceives that another is engaging in behavior that prevents or hinders their goals (Coughlan et al., 2001). Researchers working across disciplines have recognized conflict as a major issue affecting both organizational and supply chain performance (Bradford et al., 2004; Lam et al., 2007; Blackhurst et al., 2008; Molnár et al., 2010).

Due to the competitive business environment, which has been fueled by rising customer requirements and globalization, companies have been pushed to compete not just with their own capabilities but also with their entire supply chain and suppliers (Christopher, 1992; Barutcu et al., 2010). Under these circumstances, coordination and management of entities in supply chains have proven to be a challenging task due to the conflicts inherent in such systems. If not managed effectively, the conflicts can impact supply chain network performance and lead to dissolution of network partnerships. The supply chain network is a system full of contradictions and conflicts, thus understanding the reasons for conflicts and the motivations of business parties is crucial for elaborating the nature and complexity of conflicts. The insight gathered from the profound examination of conflicts and conflict resolution strategies adopted in diverse industries would enable the comprehension of the reasons why some conflicts occur and end up in destructive consequences while some others constructively give rise to stronger bonds among the supply chain partners.

By the necessity of understanding supply chain conflicts in a deeper sense, we aim to shed light on the aspects of previous supply chain conflict literature. This study contributes to the existing literature by pointing to the areas of conflicts and effective conflict resolution methods employed in various types of supply chains. In this way, we also aim to provide insights for the development of proactive conflict handling strategies for practitioners. Additionally, this study categorizes and redefines conflict areas and different conflict resolution mechanisms employed in different B2B relationships in prior academic studies. In this regard, our paper aims to systematically review and assess the status of research for providing a framework for future research avenues. With this aim, we address the following research questions:

RQ1. What are the current conflict areas for B2B supply chains?

RQ2. Which conflict resolution mechanisms can be applied for conflicts in B2B supply chains?

RQ3. What are the possible future research avenues for B2B supply chain conflicts?

The remainder of this research is as follows; first, we explain a brief overview of supply chain conflicts by basing on different industries and different supply chain perspectives along with the applied conflict resolutions methods.

Then, we explain the methodology used in this study including details of its scope, data collection process and data analysis procedures. Findings, future research directions and implications of this review study are presented in the following sections.

2. Literature Review

Referring to the review studies so far, we see that some of the conflicts are examined on an industry basis (Barutcu et al., 2010; Jaffar et al., 2011; Pereseina et al., 2014; Aithal & Maurya, 2017), some of them are handled with different supply chain perspectives (Kanda & Deshmukh, 2008; John & Prasad, 2012; Zhou, 2012; Johnsen & Lacoste, 2016) and some of them are written with a general perspective like ours (Coughlan et al., 2001; Constantinescu, 2017).

In diverse industries, conflicts have some similar and distinguishing patterns and sources. For instance, Barutcu et al. (2010) ascertained that conflicts and resolution methods in the textile industry differ between downstream and upstream partners. Herein main sources of conflict are found as price changes for downstream partners and demands for faster delivery from upstream partners. The basic conflict resolution methods used are compromising for downstream partners and sharing for upstream partners. Similarly, Jaffar et al. (2011) provided an overview about conflict reasons in the construction industry and highlighted three types of conflict factors as behavioral problems, contractual problems, and technical problems. In similar lines, Pereseina et al. (2014) explored the challenges and conflicts in automobile and logistics industries in which conflicts are addressed from environmental and economic perspectives. Lastly, Aithal & Maurya (2017) presented main reasons for channel conflicts in the context of the retail industry and highlighted probable outcomes of perceived channel conflicts.

In the literature, conflicts are also addressed from different supply chain perspectives in reviewed papers conducted so far. Within the scope of supply chain coordination, Kanda & Deshmukh (2008) pointed to typical conflicts in supply chain processes and proposed a conflict resolution framework based on the use of coordination mechanisms. In parallel to this research, John & Prasad (2012) examined conflicts specifically in purchasing situations, design, marketing and distribution channels, and workflows with the consideration of effective supply chain coordination to understand and appreciate different conflict detection methods. In line with the organizational behavior perspective, Zhou (2012) simply listed five fundamental areas of supply chain conflict and they put forward a three-dimensional conflict resolution model accordingly to distinguish the behavioral intentions of companies in the supply chain. From the perspective of channel relationships, Johnsen & Lacoste (2016) sketched out an integrated heuristic map of the literature on situations spurring customer-supplier conflicts with two sub-topics: the main reasons for conflict related to asymmetric relationships and opportunism and other reasons along with the different types of conflict (e.g., lack of role clarity, cultural differences etc.).

By adopting a more general perspective, Coughlan et al. (2001) suggested a taxonomy with three pillars: goal incompatibility, different perceptions of reality, and domain conflicts as the sources of conflict. Additionally, Constantinescu (2017) plotted a diagram of supply chain conflict areas in eight classifications: logistics, quality, commercial, management, financial, relationship along the chain, business environment and interpersonal communication.

Apart from the “literature reviews”, there are also studies that examine the conflict in general with meta-analytical review and bibliometric analysis (Sharma & Parida, 2018; Caputo et al., 2019). In this regard, while Sharma & Parida (2018) suggested that determinants/antecedents of conflicts can be categorized into three main areas: organizational, interpersonal (communication, collaboration, relational activities, and opportunistic behavior), and environmental (environmental volatility, product or market volatility and competitive intensity), Caputo et al. (2019) identified key issues that help guide the direction of conflict management research: negotiation, mediation, trust, conflict management styles, and performance.

As the existing literature contains little review research presenting a detailed descriptive analysis with the integration of content analysis of the supply chain conflicts and resolution, this review is considered to be filling an important gap. In this research, we reveal the sources/areas of conflicts reflected in the related previous studies with a wider perspective by also looking at resolution mechanisms employed. Additionally, conflict resolution (CR) mechanisms provide a foundation to solve the problems faced, but there is limited research focusing on how business partners select the most appropriate CR strategy in their current situational context. Therefore, apart from the theoretical contribution, we aimed to offer a managerial contribution by proposing a classification of how to apply the knowledge of conflicts including how to evaluate and select resolution methods/approaches depending on the sources/areas of conflict for business managers. Furthermore, with the provided future research directions, our study can guide the forthcoming studies by highlighting the research gaps and opportunities in the related field.

3. Methodology

Given the changes that have impacted supply chain management research over the past decade, such as the emergence of global sourcing, potential disruptions, increased importance of responsiveness and high level of agility, a clear and up-to-date documentation of key themes, concepts, and relationships in the conflict field is needed. Similarly, it is observed that many systematic literature studies in supply chain management have examined a 10-year time period (e.g., Soosay and Hyland, 2015; Singh and Trivedi, 2016; Caputo et al., 2018; Al Naimi et al., 2022; Jaiswal and Samuel, 2023). Therefore, this study proposes a literature analysis covering the years from 2010 to 2021 with an aim to create a systematic review that is comparable and consistent with previous assessments in the field of conflict management (Caputo et al., 2018).

The research was conducted using “Web of Science” Clarivate Analytics Web of Science Core Collection database which is recognized as the most reliable database for bibliometric studies (Marzi et al., 2018) due to offering high-impact collection of data. Instead of limiting our subject areas as Environmental Science, Social Sciences, and Business, Management, and Accounting, we included all categories for rendering an interdisciplinary conflict framework. As we investigated the behaviors of different parties within a B2B context in response to potential or actual obstacles preventing one or more of the parties from achieving their goals (Coughlan et al., 2001), our initial search string included the following keywords: “conflict”, which describes the above situation best, and “supply chain” to provide a general and contemplated perspective regarding supply chain conflicts. We only included “articles” that went through a double-blind peer-reviewed process (Marzi et al., 2018). This allowed us to identify 477 articles in total.

Phase of Paper Selection

To select the articles regarding the specific aim of the paper, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined. Regarding the subject of the “conflict”, first inclusion criteria are grounded on the widely accepted definition of the conflict, which is a situation in which a channel member perceives that another channel member is engaging in behavior that prevents them from achieving their goals (Sterns & El-Ansary, 1977). In accordance with Pittaway et al. (2004), this criterion made it possible to identify articles with abstracts that focus on the conflicts among supply chain members. To this end, the abstracts of the 477 articles were read by two scholars through Rayyan, a systematic review web app for exploring and filtering searches.

Out of 477 articles, we focused on 400 articles with abstracts stressing supply chain conflicts and giving certain references to the B2B parties involved. After conducting a detailed analysis of each abstract, we additionally excluded 57 articles that were out-of-scope. The final database resulted in 343 relevant documents suitable for the analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Systematic Literature Review Process

4. Findings

Descriptive analysis

Concerning the industries, the vast majority of papers specifically addressed retail (28%), manufacturing (15%), and electronic industries (13%) (Figure 2). Herein, the manufacturing industry includes many different sectors at the same time. The humanitarian and information technologies sectors were detected as the areas where less conflict research was conducted compared to the others.

Figure 2. Distribution of Articles by Industry

Regarding the research methodology applied, the most of the papers employed quantitative techniques (76% includes mathematical modeling, case study, experiment, optimization and decentralized methods, regression, simulation, bibliometric studies) and further portion adopted qualitative methodologies (17% includes case studies, interviews, field studies, action research projects, ethnographic studies, focus groups, discourses, comparative and conceptual analysis) or mixed approaches (constitute 7% of the papers) (Figure 3-4-5).

Figure 3. Research Methodologies

Figure 4. Quantitative Research Methods

Figure 5. Qualitative Research Methods

While the most prominent theories are game, institutional and stakeholder theories, other theories include bargaining theory, transaction cost theory, social exchange theory, contingency theory, agency theory, resource dependence theory, and resource-based theory with very similar percentages (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Papers by Theories

Content analysis

Areas of conflicts

Channel members operate under different business philosophies that lead to different goals. Pursuing more than a single set of goals introduces various sources of conflict that are directly associated with the level of conflict perceived by channel members (Eliashberg & Michie, 1984). Logically, to understand and manage channel conflicts, we must first identify the determinants and sources of the conflict (Kumar & van Dissel, 1996). In consideration of the systematic literature review covering the last 11 years, Table 1 depicts the most common conflicts found as economic conflicts, operational conflicts, sustainability conflicts, and relationship conflicts.

Economic conflict is a channel member's negative feeling toward economic decline, such as decreasing profits (Yu et al., 2018). Although this concept is defined as commercial conflict (e.g., Lacity & Willcocks, 2017) in some studies and financial conflict (e.g., Beheshtifar and Zare, 2013) in others, we used the expression of "economic" as we found that everything with economic value causes conflict between partners in the supply chain. In the study, economic conflicts are disputes over finances such as price and profit margins and threaten economic performance of the companies. Our study reveals that economic conflicts in recent years are pertinent to problems with inventory/order levels, revenue sharing, specified financial targets, sales prices, distribution of resources, retail format preferences, channel encroachments and channel incentives.

Operational conflict arises when the operation of various elements of logistics systems and standards conflict such as the flow between the elements,

standards, norms, institutions, instruments, format and so on (Ge et al., 2010). In the meantime, it influences the relative preference between options in a choice set. In this review, some of the conflicts stemming from tradeoffs comprise efficiency and utilization considerations such as procurement planning, scheduling, optimal ordering and shipment size decisions, inventory control, network design, postponement/quick response, market coverage, decision timing practices, performance evaluations of partners, contract/policy design and quality evaluations. Besides, service conflicts related to service levels, after-sales service operations and demand-enhancing service operations are found to be the basis of most common operational-related conflicts experienced by business partners.

In *sustainability conflicts*, the stakeholder groups differ enormously in their values, time horizons, and resource allocations. Additionally, they may feature characteristics that present unique challenges to conflict resolution, such as large numbers of stakeholders, common resources, and specialized knowledge about the involved issues (Majer et al., 2018). In this review, sustainability conflicts are related with the considerations regarding sustainability and economic-operational outcomes (e.g., pricing, reverse logistics cost, and manufacturing cost) and refer to the strategic-level considerations in sustainability (e.g., supply chain transparency and monitoring, distribution of natural sources, crop regime shifts, land usage and compliance to government regulations).

As stated by Cai et al. (2020), *relationship conflict* is one of the types of organizational conflicts in B2B relationships. Herein, it refers to states of incompatibilities between organizational members due to inconsistent values (Cai et al., 2020) and it damages the cooperation performance of the business partners. In this sense, when looking at recent years, relational conflicts usually arise from the role conflicts of the partners, channel power practices and tactical strategies between parties, trust violations, separation of ownership and control, strong joint dependencies, partnering issues, having superior or incomplete information, misrepresentation, and manipulation of information in an opportunistic way along the supply chains.

Table 1. Areas of Conflicts

Categories	Conflict definitions and scope	Related research
Economic Conflicts	...refers profit margins and pricing related conflicts associated with inventory/order levels, revenue sharing, specified financial targets, sales prices, distribution of resources, retail format preferences, channel encroachments, and channel incentive conflicts including misalignment of incentives, incentives on pricing, quality, and investment levels, in-store promotions, offering referrals, extended warranty terms,	Chiang & Feng (2010), Biyalogorsky & Koenigsberg (2010), Frow et al. (2010), Ding et al. (2011), Cai & Chen (2011), Huang et al. (2011), Yan (2011), He & Khouja (2011), Liu et al. (2012), Heese (2012), Chyu & Huang (2013), Tripathi & Dave (2013), Panda (2014), Huang et al. (2014), Xu et al. (2015), Panda et al. (2015), Lv & Qi (2016), Li & Li (2016), Ohmura & Matsuo (2016), Yoo & Kim (2016), Lacity & Willcocks (2017), DeLuca-Acconi (2017), Jiang et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2018), Wang

	reinforcement of sales efforts, amount of discounts and return taking policies.	& Liu (2018), Saha et al. (2018), Yang et al. (2018), Biswas & Avittathur (2019), Wang et al. (2019), Li et al. (2020), Cai & Qing (2020), Xia et al. (2021), Li and Li (2021), Li et al. (2021), Xiao et al. (2021), Zhao et al. (2021), Zhao & Li (2021), Hou et al. (2021), Yan & Ye (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Yang et al. (2021), Zheng & Yu (2021), Lin et al. (2021), Wang et al. (2021), Modak et al. (2021), Lin et al. (2021), Tang et al. (2021), Ma & Hong (2021), Huang et al. (2021), Jiao et al. (2021), Hu et al. (2021), Loconto et al. (2021)
Operational Conflicts	...refer to operational conflicts stemming from efficiency and utilization considerations such as procurement planning, scheduling, optimal ordering and shipment size decisions, inventory control, network design, postponement/quick response, market coverage, decision timing practices, performance evaluations of partners, contract/policy designs and quality evaluations, and service conflicts related to service levels, after sales service operations , trade-in and demand-enhancing service operations.	Wang et al. (2010), Steward et al. (2010), Liu et al. (2012), Ramezani et al. (2013), Kurata & Ham (2013), Karimi-Nasab et al. (2013), Zhou et al. (2014), Selviaridis & Norrman (2014), Park & Lee (2015), Ab Rahman et al. (2016), Matawale et al. (2016), Li et al. (2016), Yildiz et al. (2016), Vairaktarakis & Aydinliyim (2017), Rasmussen et al. (2017), Fan et al. (2017), Kuik et al. (2017), Seif et al. (2018), Nielsen & Saha (2018), Elkhechafi et al. (2018), Niu & Xie (2020), Tang & Yang (2020), Jiang et al. (2020), Lin & Wang (2020), Vishnu et al. (2020), Shen & Qian (2021), Yoo and Cheong (2021), Pourmohammad-Zia et al. Rezaei (2021), Karray & Martín-Herrán (2021), Idris et al. (2021), Svanberg et al. (2021), Suleiman et al. (2021), Hamamura & Zenny (2021)
Sustainability Conflicts	...refer to the considerations regarding sustainability and economic-operational-social outcomes (e.g., pricing, reverse logistics cost and manufacturing cost). These conflicts may also refer to the strategic-level considerations in sustainability (e.g., supply chain transparency and monitoring, distribution of natural sources, crop regime shifts, compliance to government regulations, land usage, implementation of sustainability practices).	Ni et al. (2010), Sherval & Hardiman (2014), Inghelbrecht et al. (2014), Grose & Richardson (2014), Modak et al. (2016), Huang et al. (2016), Svensson et al. (2016), Qin et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2018), Li et al. (2018), Mantino & Frosina (2018), Arrigo (2018), Rebehy et al. (2019), Hosseini-Motlagh et al. (2019), Wijen & Chiroleu-Assouline (2019), Zheng et al. (2019), Guo et al. (2020), Zarei et al. (2020), Alizadeh-Basban & Taleizadeh (2020), Goworek et al. (2020), Karaosman et al. (2020), Kumar et al. (2021), Cruz-Daraviña & Suescún (2021), Nath & Eweje (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Fan et al. (2021), Tamannaie et al. (2021), Vlachokostas et al. (2021)

<p>Relationship Conflicts</p>	<p>...refer to the partner role/responsibility conflicts, personal relationships, over-relying, channel power practices (e.g., coercive, reward) and tactical strategies between parties, trust violations, separation of ownership and controls, strong joint dependencies, partnering issues, self-serving and free riding behaviors, and having superior or incomplete information. These conflicts also refer to misrepresentation and manipulation of information in an opportunistic way along the supply chains.</p>	<p>Cheng (2011), Oosterhuis et al. (2012), Mysen et al. (2012), Lumineau & Henderson (2012), Salonen & Gabrielsson (2012), Cheng & Sheu (2012), Cheng & Fu (2013), Leber et al. (2014), Egels-Zandén Hulthén, & Wulff (2015), Addae-Boateng et al. (2015), Peres & Kesan (2015), Chang & Fang (2015), Dong et al. (2016), Perner & Skjølsvik (2016), Low & Lee (2016), Murfield et al. (2016), Panchal et al. (2017), Madichie & Yamoah (2017), Awan et al. (2018), Low (2018), Eckerd & Sweeney (2018), Dwivedi et al. (2018), Chen & Xu (2018), Qian et al. (2018), Yang et al. (2018), Akrouf et al. (2018), Yan et al. (2019), Butt (2019), Pulles & Loohuis (2020), Høgevoid, et al. (2020), Talay et al. (2020), Shareef et al. (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Vos et al. (2021), Tolmay (2021), Badenhorst-Weiss & Tolmay (2021), Guo et al. (2021), Ma et al. (2021), Richards & Safari (2021), Matthes et al. (2021)</p>
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Conflict Resolution

In this study, by enlarging the conflict resolution definition, we consider resolution mechanisms/methods employed in reviewed papers as different ways of achieving resolution with the best possible outcomes in the supply chain conflicts. In this sense, the paper reviews the current state of knowledge in conflict areas and resolution mechanisms by offering a projection to support contemporary theory and practice.

Resolution of the conflicts in social sciences

Conflict resolution is defined as strategies aimed at increasing, reducing, and resolving tension (Dreu et al., 1999) and it is characterized as an interaction process in which two parties react and act on each other, with individuals changing their behavior to adapt to the situation and attain the best possible results (Munduate et al., 1999; Coleman & Kugler, 2014). Within the context of organizational conflict, widely applied conflict resolution methods revolve around institutional information intensive mechanisms, third party mechanisms, using incentives, relational governance mechanisms, contractual governance mechanisms (Lumineau & Malhotra, 2011; Palmatier et al., 2020; Ryciuk, 2020; Shahzad et al., 2020). Herein, institutionalized information intensive mechanisms can be in forms of joint memberships in trade associations, distributor councils, and exchange-of-personnel programs. In this context, members create “information intensive mechanisms” by sharing information and devoting resources to communicating for resolution of channel conflicts. Moreover, building relational governance based on

informal mechanisms such as trust, reciprocity or social embedding, or providing contractual governance by defining the roles and duties of the parties are some of the efficient ways to deal with conflict. Similarly, for all players involved in the conflict resolution process, relying on third parties, which are external parties, not involved in the channel like referrals to boards of arbitration or mediation and aligning some economic incentives offer a way out before the conflict gets much worse.

Resolution of conflicts in interdisciplinary management

Apart from social sciences, conflicts and their solutions are frequently studied in the field of interdisciplinary management.

As conflict is defined as the perception of incompatible activity in which one person's action is believed to make another less likely or effective (Cloven & Roloff, 1991), some papers focus on the reduction of incompatibility among the players. In this context, stakeholder groups may not understand conflict situations in the same way, which impact conflict resolution strategies. With a sensemaking perspective, the focus is on understanding the parties through the development of meanings and how those meanings motivate their involvement, actions, and practices in the conflict resolution process (Brummans, et al., 2008; Mikkelsen, 2012).

Additionally, conflict-resolution methods can be adopted as practical approaches to address the contradictions and trade-offs between the stakeholders involved (Alizadeh et al., 2017). Within this scope, game theoretical models and multi-objective optimization methods are used on a large scale in resolving problems related to conflicting interests of different decision makers (Lee, 2012; Tang & Liao, 2021). With game theoretical models, actions of the parties involved are considered simultaneously. In this respect, conflict resolution models are designed based on game-theoretic rough sets by constructing a game between all involved parties computing the payoff of different strategies, and classifying them according to equilibrium rules (Bashir et al., 2021). On the other hand, multi-objective optimization methods, which include different interests and goals of stakeholders, are conducted to find an optimal alternative considering the level of conflict and impact of conflict alternatives to select a combination of conflict resolution alternatives (Lee et al., 2017). The alternatives are evaluated based on the selected criteria (Sanayei et al., 2010).

In Table 2 and 3, we present the conflict areas where these resolution mechanisms are used, and the specific applications adopted by supply chain members.

Table 2. Resolution Mechanisms for Supply Chain Conflicts in Social Sciences

<p>1. Institutional information intensive mechanisms</p>	<p>...refer to using cooperative social interaction and open discussion processes, assisting timely communication, and using improved communication technologies to facilitate business practices, sharing of expertise (know-how) for solving channel conflicts.</p>	<p><u>Relationship conflicts</u> -channel power practices -having superior information -power practices and tactical strategies -opportunistic behavior -information asymmetries -free riding behavior <u>Sustainability conflicts</u> -implementing sustainability practices <u>Operational conflicts</u> -performance measurement</p>	<p>Khoja et al. (2010), Li et al. (2011), Akrouf (2014), Loosemore & Lim (2015), Low (2018), Qian et al. (2018), Tolmay (2019), Yaroson et al. (2021), Guo et al. (2021), Nath & Eweje (2021), Suleiman et al. (2021), Ma et al. (2021), Richards & Safari (2021), Matthes et al. (2021).</p>
<p>2. Relational governance mechanisms</p>	<p>...refer to developing personal relationships to provide the basis for the strong initial trust, reaching shared understanding, proposing co-creative win-win solutions, sharing cost, resources, and capabilities, developing more coordinated and better performing business environments.</p>	<p><u>Relationship conflicts</u> -opportunistic behaviors -information asymmetry -power practices and tactical strategies -absence of personal relationships -self serving behaviors -over relying <u>Sustainability conflicts</u> -crop regime shifts -decisions regarding sustainability and economic-operational outcomes -land use <u>Economic conflicts</u></p>	<p>Frow et al. (2010), Khoja et al. (2010), Steward et al. (2010), Chen et al. (2010), Lumineau & Malhotra (2011), Lumineau & Henderson (2012), Mysen et al. (2012), Inghelbrecht et al. (2014), Selviaridis & Norrman (2014), Xhoxhi et al. (2014), Loosemore & Lim (2015), Park & Lee (2015), Addae-Boateng et al. (2015), Han & Chuang (2015), Yoo & Kim (2016), Yan et al. (2016), Liu et al. (2018), Eckerd & Sweeney (2018), Akrouf et al. (2018), Butt (2019), Enz et al. (2019), Tolmay (2019), Chen et al. (2019), Høgevold et al. (2020), Badenhorst-Weiss & Tolmay (2021), Cruz-Daraviña & Suescún (2021), Prakash et al. (2021)</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -retail format preferences -specified financial targets -sales prices -channel encroachments -payment terms <u>Operational conflicts</u> -efficiency considerations (SKU rationalization) - contract design -procurement planning -quality issues 	
3. Contractual governance mechanisms	...refer using formal and detailed written contracts delineating the responsibilities of each party and specifying the appropriate actions in conflict resolution.	<u>Relationship conflicts</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -opportunistic behaviors -information asymmetry -manipulation of information -separation of ownership and control - strong joint dependency -power practices -over-relying <u>Operational conflicts</u> -contract designs and inefficiencies 	Khoja et al. (2010), Lumineau & Malhotra (2011), Lumineau & Henderson (2012), Selviaridis & Norrman (2014), Addae-Boateng et al. (2015), Bai et al. (2016), Low & Lee (2016), Eckerd & Sweeney (2018), Dwivedi et al. (2018), Awan et al., (2018), Shen & Qian (2021), Prakash et al. (2021).
4. Third party mechanisms	...refer to third parties for conflict resolutions in terms of negotiation, mediation, arbitration, or upper industrial regulatory institutions.	<u>Relationship conflicts</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -trust violations -opportunistic behaviors -power practices <u>Sustainability conflicts</u> -decisions regarding sustainability and economic-operational outcomes 	Wang & Song (2011), Barchiesi et al. (2014), Peres & Kesan (2015), Low & Lee (2016), Yu et al. (2017), Rebehay et al. (2019)

<p>5. Using incentives</p>	<p>...refer to conducting compensation mechanisms, aligning, and specifying the responsibilities and incentives along the channels.</p>	<p><u>Economic conflicts</u> -retail format preferences -profit considerations <u>Operational conflicts</u> -quality evaluations -ordering and inventory decisions <u>Relationship conflicts</u> -partners roles and responsibilities -interest alignment -power exercises -opportunism</p>	<p>Taek et al. (2010), Crosno & Dahlstrom (2011), Low & Lee (2016), Kong et al. (2017), Tse et al. (2018), Low (2018), Yang et al. (2019), Liu et al. (2020), Nguyen (2020), Li et al. (2021), Ma & Hong (2021)</p>
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Table 3. Resolution Mechanisms for Supply Chain Conflicts in Interdisciplinary

Management

<p>1. Sense-making activities</p>	<p>...refer to acts having an impact on the decision-making process of the conflicting parties like persuasion, cognitive mapping and aggregation, diagnostic prognostic and motivational framing and goal recognition among parties.</p>	<p><u>Relationship conflicts</u> -role conflicts -trust violations <u>Sustainability conflicts</u> - decisions regarding sustainability and social-environmental outcomes <u>Operational conflicts</u> -policy design</p>	<p>Oosterhuis et al. (2012), Guarnieri et al. (2016), Yu et al. (2017), Rasmussen et al. (2017), DeLuca-Acconi (2017)</p>
<p>2. Game theoretical models</p>	<p>...refer to constructing a game for solving supply chain conflicts by using backward induction, equilibrium strategies, robustness approaches, price-theoretic models, bargaining strategies and</p>	<p><u>Economic conflicts</u> -channel encroachments -revenue sharing -contract design -double marginalization -extended warranty terms <u>Sustainability conflicts</u> - strategic-level considerations in sustainability (e.g.,</p>	<p>Cai (2010), Cai (2011), Heese (2012), Kurata & Ham (2013), Panda (2014), Huang et al. (2014), Panda et al. (2015), Guan & Chen (2015), Xu et al. (2015), Modak et al. (2016), Ohmura & Matsuo (2016), Panda et al. (2016), Bashinskaya et al. (2016), Yang & Gao (2017), Zhang & Wang (2017), Yang & Gao (2017), Saha et al. (2018), Liu et al.</p>

	coordinating contracts.	crop regime, supply chain transparency and responsible sourcing) - decisions regarding sustainability and economic- environmental outcomes <u>Operational conflicts</u> - performance evaluations -optimal inventory levels -market coverage -decision timing practices -offering trade-in services -after sales service operations <u>Relationship conflicts</u> -role conflicts -information asymmetry	(2018), Fahimnia et al. (2018), Modak et al. (2018), Yan et al. (2019), Chen & Su (2019), Huang & Zhang (2020), Zu (2021), Chen (2021), Li and Li (2021), Xiao et al. (2021), Pourmohammad- Zia, Karimi & Rezaei (2021), Kumar et al. (2021), Zhao & Li (2021), Hou et al. (2021), Yan & Ye (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Karray & Martín-Herrán (2021), Yang et al. (2021), Zheng & Yu (2021), Lin et al. (2021), Wang et al. (2021), Panda et al. (2021), Lin et al. (2021), Liu et al. (2021), Huang et al. (2021), Tamannaei, Zarei & Rasti-Barzoki (2021), Li & Du (2021), Hu et al. (2021)
3. Multi-Objective Optimization Models	...refer to finding an optimal solution for supply chain conflicts by considering a combination of alternatives using heuristic, metaheuristic, and combinations of them, fuzzy algorithms, network and simulation models, and constrained optimization.	<u>Economic conflicts</u> -profit considerations -incentives on quality levels <u>Operational conflicts</u> -partner selection -optimal order quantity and inventory levels -network design -procurement planning -scheduling <u>Relationship conflicts</u> -incomplete information -power dominances <u>Sustainability conflicts</u>	Güneri et al. (2011), Liu et al. (2012), Manoj et al. (2012), Ramezani et al. (2013), Aliakbari Nouri et al.(2015), Yildiz et al. (2016), Vairaktarakis & Aydinliyim (2017), Qin et al. (2017), Liu et al. (2018), Elkhechafi et al. (2018), Seif et al. (2018), Vishnu et al. (2020), Yoo and Cheong (2021), Tang et al. (2021), Fan et al. (2021), Vlachokostas et al. (2021).

		- decisions regarding sustainability and economic-environmental outcomes	
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Associating conflict areas with resolution methods in B2B supply chain context, it can be detected that economic conflicts are mostly resolved with relational governance, or by using incentives, game-theoretical and multi-objective optimization models. We also realized that in the literature on operational conflict, various mechanisms are being employed such as relational and contractual governance mechanisms, using incentives, institutional information intensive mechanisms, sense-making activities, game theoretical models and multi-objective optimization. In terms of sustainability conflicts, relational governance, third party mechanisms, institutional information intensive mechanisms, sense making, game-theoretical models and multi-objective optimization are mostly applied resolution tools. Finally, for relationship conflicts, the parties involved use all of the methods effectively (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Conflict Area Based Resolution Mechanisms

Future Opportunities

Grounding on the systematic literature review that we have conducted and by capturing the recent articles in the field (e.g., Karaosman et al., 2020; Lin & Wang, 2020; Vishnu et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2020), we formulate some research

questions for guiding the possible future studies. In this regard, channel coordination issues, supply chain relationships, and environmental uncertainties are found to extend the extant anecdotal and conceptual body of literature by generating additional value for research and practice.

Concerning supply chain relations and coordination problems, the role of conflict resolution mechanisms in preventing different conflict outcomes is an area that researchers can focus on. As another avenue, the role of institutional pressures in conflict resolution in supply chains appeared to be one of the promising areas for further research. Along similar lines, the effects of omnichannel service collaboration and the effect of developments in internet-based technologies require more attention from the academic field. Moreover, prevention of conflicts under information asymmetry situations and varying response strategies under different circumstances (e.g., the severe threat of competition or cooperation between partners) are the other fruitful areas to proceed.

Pursuant to the environmental uncertainties, setting constructive conflict management strategies and reconfiguring internal and external capabilities in turbulent business environments emerge as important research areas with research gaps. Additionally, considering the emergency situations and disruptions, demonstrating common conflicts and resolution methods by pursuing responsiveness are identified as flourishing directions worth working on. In this direction, we group these recommendations by conceptions in Table 4.

Table 4. Recommendations and Research Questions for Future Research

Recommendation	Research question for future research
<p>Supply Chain Relations and Coordination Problems</p> <p>Researchers should explore channel coordination problems where all members aim to maximize their own interest. Additionally, relational dynamics and effects of relationship characteristics can be explored.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can the coordinative mechanism be used to mitigate destructive conflicts under the severe threat of competition? • How do the mimetic, coercive, and normative institutional pressures affect conflict resolution in supply chains? • How can service cooperation in multi-channels be provided to mitigate channel conflicts and improve the service levels? • In case of information asymmetries, how can coordination be facilitated in supply chains to avoid different forms of conflicts? • What is the role of behavioral factors such as anticipated regret and risk aversion on the part of decision makers in avoiding service-oriented supply chain conflicts? • How do conflict characteristics (e.g., directness and

	<p>intensity of opposition) change in the course of a business relationship?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do supply chain partners' response strategies for conflicts differ in case of cooperation situations? • In what ways recent developments in internet-based technologies (e.g., artificial intelligence and blockchain) can be effective in conflicts arising from the imbibing of strategic capabilities into supply chains?
<p>Environmental Uncertainties: Researchers should explore the changing characteristics of the environment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can external conditions such as future uncertainty and market complexity influence the development of constructive conflict management strategies? • How can organizations integrate, build, and reconfigure internal and external capabilities to defuse conflicts in rapidly changing environments? • What are the conflicts frequently experienced during slow onset disasters such as pandemics and climate change? Which conflict resolution strategies are being applied during slow-onset disaster related disruptions?

5. Conclusions

Although conflict research has attracted notable academic attention, this review shows that existing review research, which focuses empirical evidence on very specific aspects, has deficits in categorizing and defining current conflicts and their sub-branches from a broader perspective. Due to the upsurging volume of international business operations, effectively coordinating the interests of supply chain members and building a suitable mode of conflict resolution deserves attention. By means of this research, apart from the divergence of resolution methods in studies, the tools used in these methods are also mentioned. By adhering to conflict resolution literature, we revealed the different resolution methods for supply chain conflicts by drawing a novel framework. From all these respects, this area can provide valuable and important insights both for practitioners and researchers.

In summary, the following six implications can be derived from the research questions. First, the industry analysis shows that manufacturing and retail sectors are actively studied areas where various types of conflict coexist. Sectors open to research in supply conflict management have also been identified. Second, in recent years, it is detected that there are many conflict studies using quantitative methodologies. In this sense, it is thought that different conflict areas mentioned in the “future opportunities” part will be valuable when using qualitative and mixed methodology. Third, the theory analysis demonstrated that game, institutional, and stakeholder theories are found to be matching well with the scope of conflicts. Fourth, the most common conflict areas are related to economic, operational, sustainability, and relationship conflicts. Fifth, it is found that

chosen resolution mechanisms in different fields of research vary depending on the area of the conflict. It is also observed that resolution strategies differ from previous studies as we adopt interdisciplinary conflict frameworks, which capture different aspects of the conflict. Within this scope, while institutional information-intensive mechanisms, relational governance mechanisms, contractual governance mechanisms, third party mechanisms, using incentives are widely used resolution methods in social sciences; sense-making activities, game-theoretical models, and multi-objective optimization methods are widely applied in interdisciplinary management for B2B supply chain conflicts. Finally, we suggest that supply chain relations and coordination problems as well as environmental uncertainties in business environments are promising topics for future research. In this context, considering the impact of the epidemic, supply chain relations and coordination issues can be explored in parallel to turbulent business environments.

This research provides a snapshot of knowledge for academics, providing a comprehensive analysis of research designs, methodologies, and findings by researchers in the field. In this way, it contributes to the industrial marketing and international marketing literature while revealing the phenomenon of conflict and future research directions. This study also enables managers and practitioners to be aware of the existence of different supply chain-based conflicts and to manage the conflicts more effectively. Besides, by providing the resolution mechanisms for conflict areas, this study sheds light on the possible resolution generation strategies for the encountered supply chain conflicts.

It should also be noted that the results of this study are to be seen within limitations. First, the reviewed studies were obtained from English-language journals only key word specific. Second, this study only considers peer-reviewed international journals, thus excluding publications in other forms such as books and conference proceedings. Third, although this study provides a holistic systematic literature regarding supply chain conflicts and resolution methods, it needs to be further deepened with more empirical research testing.

REFERENCES

- Ab Rahman, M. N., Leuveano, R. A. C., bin Jafar, F. A., Saleh, C., Deros, B. M., Mahmood, W. M. F. W., and Mahmood, W. H. W. (2016). Incorporating logistic costs into a single vendor–buyer JELS model. *Applied Mathematical Modeling* 40 (23): 10809-10819.
- Addae-Boateng, S., Wen, X., and Brew, Y. (2015). Contractual governance, relational governance, and firm performance: The case of Chinese and Ghanaian and family firms. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 5(5): 288.
- Aithal, R. K., and Maurya, H. (2017). Exploring channel conflict in an emerging economy: the small retailer’s perspective. *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management* 45(10): 1061-1078.
- Akrouf, H. (2014). Relationship quality in cross-border exchanges: A temporal perspective. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 21(3): 145-169.
- Akrouf, H., Kaswengi, J., and Valette-Florence, P. (2018). Business marketing in France: can the case be made for “French exceptionalism” or is it just a slight variation? *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 25(3): 187-211.
- Al Naimi, M., Faisal, M. N., Sobh, R., & Bin Sabir, L. (2022). A systematic mapping review exploring 10 years of research on supply chain resilience and

reconfiguration. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 25(8), 1191-1218.

Aliakbari Nouri, F., Khalili Esbouei, S., and Antucheviciene, J. (2015). A hybrid MCDM approach based on fuzzy ANP and fuzzy TOPSIS for technology selection. *Informatica* 26(3): 369-388.

Alizadeh, M. R., Nikoo, M. R., and Rakhshandehroo, G. R. (2017). Developing a multi-objective conflict-resolution model for optimal groundwater management based on fallback bargaining models and social choice rules: a case study. *Water Resources Management* 31(5): 1457-1472.

Alizadeh-Basban, N., and Taleizadeh, A. A. (2020). A hybrid circular economy-Game theoretical approach in a dual-channel green supply chain considering sale's effort, delivery time, and hybrid remanufacturing. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 250: 119521.

Arrigo, E. (2018). The flagship stores as sustainability communication channels for luxury fashion retailers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 44: 170-177.

Awan, U., Kraslawski, A., and Huiskonen, J. (2018). Governing interfirm relationships for social sustainability: the relationship between governance mechanisms, sustainable collaboration, and cultural intelligence. *Sustainability* 10(12): 4473.

Badenhorst-Weiss, J. A., & Tolmay, A. S. (2021). Trust, commitment and business expansion in automotive supply chains in a developing country: a principal-agency perspective. *International Journal of Applied Management Science*, 13(1), 52-68.

Bai, X., Sheng, S., and Li, J. J. (2016). Contract governance and buyer-supplier conflict: The moderating role of institutions. *Journal of Operations Management* 41: 12-24.

Barchiesi, M. A., Costa, R., baand Greco, M. (2014). Enhancing conflict resolution through an AHP-based methodology. *International Journal of Management and Decision Making* 13(1): 17-41.

Barutcu, S., Dogan, H., Barutcu, E., and Kulakli, A. (2010). Supply chain-based conflict: a study from textile exporters' perspectives. *Journal of Global Strategic Management* 4(2): 90-102.

Bashinskaya, A. Y. E., Koroleva, M. V. E., and Zenkevich, N. A. E. (2016). Coordinating contracts in cooperative supply networks. *Contributions to Game Theory and Management* 9(0): 7-101.

Bashir, Z., Mahnaz, S., and Abbas Malik, M. G. (2021). Conflict resolution using game theory and rough sets. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems* 36(1): 237-259.

Beheshtifar, M., & Zare, E. (2013). Interpersonal conflict: A substantial factor to organisational failure. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(5), 400.

Biswas, I., and Avittathur, B. (2019). Channel coordination using options contract under simultaneous price and inventory competition. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 123:45-60.

Biyalogorsky, E., and Koenigsberg, O. (2010). Ownership coordination in a channel: Incentives, returns, and negotiations. *Quantitative Marketing and Economics* 8(4): 461-490.

Blackhurst, J., Wu, T. T., and Craighead, C. W. (2008). A systematic approach for supply chain conflict detection with a hierarchical Petri Net extension. *Omega* 36(5): 680-696.

Bradford, K.D., Stringfellowb, A., Weitzc, B.A. (2004). Managing conflict to improve the effectiveness of retail networks. *Journal of Retailing* 80: 181-195.

Brummans, B. H., Putnam, L. L., Gray, B., Hanke, R., Lewicki, R. J., and Wiethoff, C. (2008). Making sense of intractable multi party conflict: A study of framing in four environmental disputes. *Communication Monographs* 75(1): 25-51.

Butt, A. S. (2019). Absence of personal relationship in a buyer-supplier relationship: case of buyers and suppliers of logistics services provider in Australia. *Heliyon* 5(6): e01799.

Cai, G. G. (2010). Channel selection and coordination in dual-channel supply chains. *Journal of Retailing* 86 (1): 22-36.

Cai, G. G., and Chen, Y. J. (2011). In-store referrals on the internet. *Journal of Retailing* 87(4): 563-578.

Cai, H., and Qing, S. (2020). Pricing Strategies in a Two-Echelon Supply Chain with Sales Efforts and Channel Conflicts. *IEEE Access* 8: 83238-83247.

Cai, J., Cheng, J., Shi, H., and Feng, T. (2020). The impact of organizational conflict on green supplier integration: the moderating role of governance mechanism. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*: 1-18.

Caputo A., Marzi, G., Maley J, and Silic, M. (2019). Ten years of conflict management research 2007–2017: An update on themes, concepts and relationships. *International Journal of Conflict Management* 30(1): 87-110

Chang, Y. S., and Fang, S. R. (2015). Enhancing export performance for business markets: effects of interorganizational relationships on export market orientation (EMO). *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 22(3): 211-228.

Chen, C. H. (2021). Applying game theory in Newsvendor's supply chain model. *Journal of Information and Optimization Sciences*, 42(6), 1367-1382.

Chen, C., and Xu, C. (2018). Negotiation Optimization Strategy of Collaborative Procurement with Supply Chain Based on Multi-Agent System. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2018.

Chen, J., Liang, L., and Yao, D. Q. (2019). Factory encroachment and channel selection in an outsourced supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics* 215: 73-83.

Chen, T. C., Hsu, C. H., Chen, C. Y., and Lii, P. (2010). Constructing virtual channel power model. *African Journal of Business Management* 4(12): 2430-2437.

Chen, Z., and Su, S. I. I. (2019). Social welfare maximization with the least subsidy: Photovoltaic supply chain equilibrium and coordination with fairness concern. *Renewable Energy* 132: 1332-1347.

Cheng, J. H. (2011). Inter-organizational relationships and information sharing in supply chains. *International Journal of Information Management* 31(4): 374-384.

Cheng, J. H., and Fu, Y. C. (2013). Inter-organizational relationships and knowledge sharing through the relationship and institutional orientations in supply chains. *International Journal of Information Management* 33(3): 473-484.

Cheng, J. H., and Sheu, J. B. (2012). Inter-organizational relationships and strategy quality in green supply chains—Moderated by opportunistic behavior and dysfunctional conflict. *Industrial Marketing Management* 41(4): 563-572.

Chiang, W. K., and Feng, Y. (2010). Retailer or e-tailer? Strategic pricing and economic-lot-size decisions in a competitive supply chain with drop-shipping. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* 61(11): 1645-1653.

Christopher, M. (1992). *Logistics and Supply Chain Management: Strategies for Reducing Costs and Improving Services*, Pitman Publishing, London.

Chyu, C. C., and Huang, I. (2013). Coordination scheme for restructuring business operation of the single period newsvendor problem. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2013.

Cloven, D. H., and Roloff, M. E. (1991). Sense-making activities and interpersonal conflict: Communicative cures for the mulling blues. *Western Journal of Communication (includes Communication Reports)* 55(2): 134-158.

- Coleman, P. T., and Kugler, K. G. (2014). Tracking managerial conflict adaptivity: Introducing a dynamic measure of adaptive conflict management in organizations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 35(7): 945-968.
- Constantinescu, G. C. (2017). Sources of Supply Chain Conflicts—A Fishbone Diagram Correlation. *SEA—Practical Application of Science* 2017(13): 191-197.
- Coughlan, A. T., Anderson, E., Stern, L. W., and El-Ansary, A. I. (2001). *Marketing Channels* (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Crosno, J. L., and Dahlstrom, R. (2011). Fairness heuristics and the fundamental transformation in interorganizational relationships. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 18(4): 313-334.
- Cruz-Daraviña, P. A., & Suescún, J. P. B. (2021). Freight operations in city centers: A land use conflict in urban planning. *Land Use Policy*, 108, 105575.
- Daft, L. Richard. (1997). *Management*, 4th Edition, The Dryden Press, Florida, USA.
- De Dreu, C.K., Harinck, F. & Van Vianen, A.E., (1999). Conflict and performance in groups and organizations. In: C.L. Cooper & I.T. Robertson, eds. *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. New York: John Wiley & Sons Ltd pp. 369-414.
- De Oliveira, U. R., Espindola, L. S., da Silva, I. R., da Silva, I. N., & Rocha, H. M. (2018). A systematic literature review on green supply chain management: Research implications and future perspectives. *Journal of cleaner production*, 187, 537-561.
- DeLuca-Acconi, R. A. (2017). Empowering social workers to transform the dominant narrative: Advocating for human rights over corporate profit. *Journal of Human Rights and Social Work* 2(1): 3-15.
- Ding, H., Guo, B., and Liu, Z. (2011). Information sharing, and profit allotment based on supply chain cooperation. *International Journal of Production Economics* 133(1): 70-79.
- Dong, M. C., Ju, M., and Fang, Y. (2016). Role hazard between supply chain partners in an institutionally fragmented market. *Journal of Operations Management* 46: 5-18.
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Shareef, M. A., Mukerji, B., Rana, N. P., and Kapoor, K. K. (2018). Involvement in the emergency supply chain for disaster management: a cognitive dissonance perspective. *International Journal of Production Research* 56 (21): 6758-6773.
- Eckerd, S. and Sweeney, K. (2018). The role of dependence and information sharing on governance decisions regarding conflict. *The International Journal of Logistics Management* 29 (1): 409-434.
- Egels-Zandén, N., Hulthén, K., and Wulff, G. (2015). Trade-offs in supply chain transparency: the case of Nudie Jeans Co. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 107: 95-104.
- Eliashberg, J., and Michie, D. A. (1984). Multiple business goals set as determinants of marketing channel conflict: An empirical study. *Journal of Marketing Research* 21(1): 75-88.
- Elkhechafi, M., Benmamoun, Z., Hachimi, H., Amine, A., and Elkettani, Y. (2018). Firefly algorithm for supply chain optimization. *Lobachevskii Journal of Mathematics* 39(2): 355-367.
- Enz, M.G., Schwieterman, M.A. and Lambert, D.M. (2019). Stock keeping unit rationalization: a cross-functional, cross-firm perspective. *The International Journal of Logistics Management* 30(4): 994-1015.
- Fahimnia, B., Jabbarzadeh, A., and Sarkis, J. (2018). Greening versus resilience: A supply chain design perspective. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 119: 129-148.

Fan, J., Ni, D., and Tang, X. (2017). Product quality choice in two-echelon supply chains under post-sale liability: insights from wholesale price contracts. *International Journal of Production Research* 55(9): 2556-2574.

Fan, Y., de Kleuver, C., de Leeuw, S., & Behdani, B. (2021). Trading off cost, emission, and quality in cold chain design: A simulation approach. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 158, 107442.

Frow, N., Marginson, D., and Ogden, S. (2010). Continuous budgeting: Reconciling budget flexibility with budgetary control. *Accounting, Organizations and Society* 35(4): 444-461.

Ge, H., Chen, L., & Li, H. (2010, January). Research on the function of the on-demand logistics mechanism in the optimization of the logistics system.

Goworek, H., Oxborrow, L., Claxton, S., McLaren, A., Cooper, T., and Hill, H. (2020). Managing sustainability in the fashion business: Challenges in product development for clothing longevity in the UK. *Journal of Business Research* 117: 629–641.

Grose, J., and Richardson, J. (2014). Strategies to identify future shortages due to interruptions in the health care procurement supply chain and their impact on health services: a method from the English National Health Service. *Journal of Health Services Research and Policy* 19(1): 19-26.

Guan, X., and Chen, Y. J. (2015). Hierarchical quality disclosure in a supply chain with cost heterogeneity. *Decision Support Systems* 76: 63-75.

Guarnieri, P., e Silva, L. C., and Levino, N. A. (2016). Analysis of electronic waste reverse logistics decisions using Strategic Options Development Analysis methodology: A Brazilian case, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 133: 1105-1117.

Güneri, A. F., Ertay, T., and Yücel, A. (2011). An approach based on ANFIS input selection and modeling for supplier selection problem. *Expert Systems with Applications* 38(12): 14907-14917.

Guo, Q., Li, Z., and Nie, J. (2020). Strategic Analysis of the Online Recycler's Reselling Channel Selection: Agency or Self-Run. *Sustainability* 12(1): 78.

Guo, W., Lu, W., Hao, L., & Gao, X. (2021). Interdependence and information exchange between conflicting parties: the role of interorganizational trust. *IEEE transactions on engineering management*.

Hamamura, J., & Zenny, Y. (2021). Retailer voluntary investment against a threat of manufacturer encroachment. *Marketing Letters*, 32(4), 379-395.

Han, I., and Chuang, C. M. (2015). The antecedents and consequences of local embeddedness: A framework based on the rice industry in Taiwan. *Asian Business and Management* 14(3): 195-226.

He, X., and Khouja, M. (2011). Pareto analysis of supply chain contracts under satisfying objectives. *European Journal of Operational Research* 214(1): 53-66.

Heese, H. S. (2012). Retail strategies for extended warranty sales and impact on manufacturer base warranties. *Decision Sciences* 43(2): 341-367.

Høgevd, N., Svensson, G., and Roberts-Lombard, M. (2020). Opportunism and conflict as precursors of non-economic and economic satisfaction outcomes in seller–customer business relationships. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 27(4): 375-395.

Hosseini-Motlagh, S. M., Govindan, K., Nematollahi, M., and Jokar, A. (2019). An adjustable bi-level wholesale price contract for coordinating a supply chain under scenario-based stochastic demand. *International Journal of Production Economics* 214: 175-195.

Hou, R., Zhao, Y., Zhu, M., & Lin, X. (2021). Price and quality decisions in a vertically-differentiated supply chain with an “Online-to-Store” channel. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 62, 102593.

Hu, Y., Qu, S., Li, G., & Sethi, S. P. (2021). Power structure and channel integration strategy for online retailers. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 294(3), 951-964.

Huang, L., and Zhang, M. (2020). Conformance Quality of the Dual-Channel Tourism Supply Chain under Tourists’ Quality Preference. *Journal of China Tourism Research*: 1-26.

Huang, L., Feng, T., & Huang, Z. (2021). Counteracting store brand introduction by the strategic incorporating of fairness concern behavior. *Nankai Business Review International*.

Huang, X., Choi, S. M., Ching, W. K., Siu, T. K., and Huang, M. (2011). On supply chain coordination for false failure returns: A quantity discount contract approach. *International Journal of Production Economics* 133(2): 634-64

Huang, X., Gu, J. W., Ching, W. K., and Siu, T. K. (2014). Impact of secondary market on consumer return policies and supply chain coordination. *Omega* 45: 57-70.

Huang, Y., Wang, K., Zhang, T., and Pang, C. (2016). Green supply chain coordination with greenhouse gases emissions management: a game-theoretic approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 112: 2004-2014.

Idris, M. N. M., Leduc, S., Yowargana, P., Hashim, H., & Kraxner, F. (2021). Spatio-temporal assessment of the impact of intensive palm oil-based bioenergy deployment on cross-sectoral energy decarbonization. *Applied Energy*, 285, 116460.

Inghelbrecht, L., Dessein, J., and Van Huylenbroeck, G. (2014). The non-GM crop regime in the EU: How do Industries deal with this wicked problem? *NJAS-Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences* 70: 103-112.

Jaffar, N., Tharim, A. A., and Shuib, M. N. (2011). Factors of conflict in construction industry: a literature review. *Procedia Engineering* 20: 193-202.

Jaiswal, A., & Samuel, C. (2023). A Literature Review Based Bibliometric Analysis of Supply Chain Analytics. *Industry 4.0 and Advanced Manufacturing*, 397-408.

Jiang, Y., Li, B., and Song, D. (2017). Analyzing consumer RP in a dual-channel supply chain with a risk-averse retailer. *European Journal of Industrial Engineering* 11(3): 271-302.

Jiang, Z. Z., He, N., Qin, X., Sun, M., and Wang, P. (2020). Optimizing production and maintenance for the service-oriented manufacturing supply chain. *Annals of Operations Research*: 1-26.

Jiao, Y., Li, Y., & Du, J. (2021). Analysis on the influence of retailer's introduction of store brand under manufacturer's product line strategy. *Journal of Industrial & Management Optimization*.

John, F. R., and Prasad, P. S. S. (2012). An overview of conflicts in supply chain systems. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management* 11(3): 325-353.

Johnsen, R. E., and Lacoste, S. (2016). An exploration of the dark side associations of conflict, power and dependence in customer–supplier relationships. *Industrial Marketing Management* 59: 76-95.

Kanda, A., and Deshmukh, S. G. (2008). Supply chain coordination: perspectives, empirical studies, and research directions. *International journal of production Economics* 115(2): 316-335.

Karaosman H., Perry P., Brun A., Morales-Alonso G. (2020). Behind the runway: extending sustainability in luxury fashion supply chains. *Journal of Business Research* 117: 652-663

Karimi-Nasab, M., Dowlatshahi, S., and Heidari, H. (2013). A multi-objective distribution-pricing model for multiperiod price-sensitive demands. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 60(3): 640-654.

Karray, S., & Martín-Herrán, G. (2021). The effects of decision timing for pricing and marketing efforts in a supply chain with competing manufacturers. *International Transactions in Operational Research*.

Khoja, F., Adams, J., and Kauffman, R. (2010). A temporal model of vertical relationships. *Journal of Business-to-business Marketing* 17(3): 279-307.

Kong, L., Liu, Z., Pan, Y., Xie, J., and Yang, G. (2017). Pricing and service decision of dual-channel operations in an O2O closed-loop supply chain. *Industrial Management and Data Systems* 117(8): 1567-1588

Kuik, S.S., Nagalingam, S., Samaranayake, P., McLean, M.W. (2017). Evaluation of recovery configuration options by product utilisation value. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management* 28: 686–710

Kumar, K., and van Diesel, H.G. (1996). Sustainable collaboration: managing conflict and cooperation in interorganizational systems. *MIS Quarterly* 20: 279-301.

Kumar, P., Baraiya, R., Das, D., Jakhar, S. K., Xu, L., & Mangla, S. K. (2021). Social responsibility and cost-learning in dyadic supply chain coordination. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 156, 102549.

Kurata, H., and Nam, S. H. (2013). After-sales service competition in a supply chain: Does uncertainty affect the conflict between profit maximization and customer satisfaction? *International journal of production economics* 144(1): 268-280.

Lacity, M., and Willcocks, L. (2017). Conflict resolution in business services outsourcing relationships. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems* 26(2): 80-100.

Lam, P.K., Chin, K.S. Pun, F.T. (2007). Managing Conflict in Collaborative New Product Development: A Supplier Perspective. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management* 24(9): 891-907.

Leber, M., Weber, C., Adam, F., and Leber, M. (2014). Mobile application as an innovative supply chain concept and the impact of social capital. *International journal of simulation modeling* 13(2): 135-146.

Lee, C. S. (2012). Multi-objective game-theory models for conflict analysis in reservoir watershed management. *Chemosphere* 87(6): 608-613.

Lee, C., Han, S. H., Jang, W., and Jung, W. (2017). Multi-objective optimization for conflict resolution in construction projects. In *9th International Structural Engineering and Construction Conference: Resilient Structures and Sustainable Construction*, ISEC 2017. ISEC Press.

Li, G., Zheng, H., Ji, X., and Li, H. (2018). Game theoretical analysis of firms' operational low-carbon strategy under various cap-and-trade mechanisms. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 197: 124-133.

Li, H., & Li, Z. (2021). Supplier Encroachment in the Supply Chain in the E-Commerce Age: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(7), 2655-2671.

Li, S., Li, M., and Zhou, N. (2020). Pricing and coordination in a dual-channel supply chain with a socially responsible manufacturer. *PloS one* 15(7): e0236099.

Li, X., Li, Y., Cai, X., and Shan, J. (2016). Service channel choice for supply chain: who is better off by undertaking the service? *Production and Operations Management* 25(3): 516-534.

Li, Y., Liu, Y., and Liu, H. (2011). Co-opetition, distributor's entrepreneurial orientation and manufacturer's knowledge acquisition: Evidence from China. *Journal of Operations Management* 29(1/2): 128-142.

Li, Y., Xiong, Y., Mariuzzo, F., & Xia, S. (2021). The underexplored impacts of online consumer reviews: Pricing and new product design strategies in the O2O supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 237, 108148.

Lin, J., Ma, X., Talluri, S., & Yang, C. H. (2021). Retail channel management decisions under collusion. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 294(2), 700-710.

Lin, X., Zhou, Y. W., & Hou, R. (2021). Impact of a “Buy-online-and-pickup-in-store” Channel on Price and Quality Decisions in a Supply Chain. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 294(3), 922-935.

Lin, Y., and Wang, X. (2020). Coopetition in the supply chain between container liners and freight forwarders: a game theory approach. *Transportation Planning and Technology* 43(8): 771-782.

Liu, A., Luo, S., Mou, J., & Qiu, H. (2021). The antagonism and cohesion of the upstream supply chain under information asymmetry. *Annals of Operations Research*, 1-46.

Liu, C., Li, X., & Liu, Q. (2021). Analysis of an evolutionary game of pallet pooling with participation of third-party platform. *Plos one*, 16(10), e0256923.

Liu, M., Liu, R., Zhu, Z., Chu, C., and Man, X. (2018). A bi-objective green closed loop supply chain design problem with uncertain demand. *Sustainability* 10(4): 967.

Liu, Y., Quan, B. T., Li, J., and Forrest, J. Y. L. (2018). A supply chain coordination mechanism with cost sharing of corporate social responsibility. *Sustainability* 10(4): 1227.

Liu, Y., S. Fang, Z. Fang, and K. Hipel. (2012). Petri net model for supply-chain quality conflict resolution of a complex product. *Kybernetes* 41(7/8): 920–928.

Liu, Y., Xia, Z. J., Shi, Q. Q., & Xu, Q. (2021). Pricing and coordination of waste electrical and electronic equipment under third-party recycling in a closed-loop supply chain. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 23(8), 12077-12094.

Liu, Y., Liu, Z.-y. and Li, J. (2020). Supply chain channel conflict coordination with consumer network acceptance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics* 33(3): 846-868.

Liu, Z., Yu, Z., Zhang, S., and Peng, J. (2018). Three stage game research of dual-channel supply chain of fresh agricultural products under consumer preference. *International Journal of Computing Science and Mathematics* 9(1): 48-57.

Loconto, A. M., Arnold, N., Silva-Castaneda, L., & Jimenez, A. (2021). Responsibilising the Fairtrade Premium: Imagining better decision-making. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 86, 711-723.

Loosemore, M., and Lim, B. (2015). Inter-organizational unfairness in the construction industry. *Construction management and economics* 33(4): 310-326.

Low, W. S. (2018). Two-step influence tactics: exploring how coercive power is exercised in channel triad. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 25(4):299-317.

Low, W. S., and Lee, H. T. (2016). The exercise and acceptance of power in an industrial channel dyad. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 23(2): 135-151.

Lumineau, F., and Henderson, J. E. (2012). The influence of relational experience and contractual governance on the negotiation strategy in buyer–supplier disputes. *Journal of Operations Management* 30(5): 382-395.

Lumineau, F., and Malhotra, D. (2011). Shadow of the contract: How contract structure shapes interfirm dispute resolution. *Strategic Management Journal* 32(5): 532-555.

Lv, B., and Qi, X. (2016). Profit allocation in collaborative product minor updates supply chain enterprises based on improved shapely value. *Journal of Advanced Mechanical Design, Systems, and Manufacturing* 10(6): 1-11.

Ma, J., & Hong, Y. (2021). Research on manufacturer encroachment with advertising and design of incentive advertising: A game-theoretic approach. *RAIRO-Operations Research*, 55, S1261-S1286.

Ma, S., Hofer, A. R., & Aloysius, J. (2021). Supplier dependence asymmetry and investment in innovation: The role of psychological uncertainty. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 27(2), 100674.

Madichie, N. O., and Yamoah, F. A. (2017). Revisiting the European horsemeat scandal: the role of power asymmetry in the food supply chain crisis. *Thunderbird International Business Review* 59(6): 663-675.

Majer, J. M., Loschelder, D. D., Windolph, L. J., and Fischer, D. (2018). How sustainability-related challenges can fuel conflict between organizations and external stakeholders: a social psychological perspective to master value differences, time horizons, and resource allocations. *Umweltpsychologie* 22(2): 53-70.

Manoj, U. V., Sriskandarajah, C., and Wagneur, E. (2012). Coordination in a two-stage production system: Complexity, conflict, and cooperation. *Computers and operations research* 39(6): 1245-1256.

Mantino, F., and Forcina, B. (2018). Market, policies and local governance as drivers of environmental public benefits: the case of the localised processed tomato in Northern Italy. *Agriculture* 8(3): 34.

Marzi, G., Caputo, A., Garces, E., and Dabić, M. (2018). A three-decade mixed-method bibliometric investigation of the IEEE transactions on engineering management. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 67(1): 4-17.

Matawale, C., Datta, S. and Mahapatra, S. (2016). Supplier/partner selection in agile supply chain: application of vague set as a decision-making tool. *Benchmarking: An International Journal* 23(7): 2027-2060.

Matthes, J. M., Saini, A., & Dubey, V. K. (2021). Performance implications of marketing agreement, cooperation, and control in franchising. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 29(3), 387-408.

Mikkelsen, E. N. (2012). Conflict and sensemaking frameworks in nonprofit organizations: An analysis of the social meanings of conflict. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly* 10:0899764012465674.

Modak, N. M., Modak, N., Panda, S., and Sana, S. S. (2018). Analyzing structure of two-echelon closed-loop supply chain for pricing, quality and recycling management. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 171: 512-528.

Modak, N. M., Panda, S., and Sana, S. S. (2016). Pricing policy and coordination for a two-layer supply chain of duopolistic retailers and socially responsible manufacturer. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications* 19(6): 487-508.

Modak, N. M., Panda, S., Sinha, S., & Ghosh, D. (2021). Implications of Contract-Bargaining Mechanisms for Coordination and Profit Sharing in a Distribution Channel. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2021.

Molnár, A., Gellynck, X., and Weaver, R. (2010). Chain member perception of chain performance: the role of relationship quality. *Journal on chain and network science* 10(1): 27-49.

Munduate, L., Ganaza, J., Peiro, J. M., and Euwema, M. C. (1999). Patterns of styles in conflict management and effectiveness, *The International Journal of Conflict Management* 10: 5-24

Murfield, M. L. U., Esper, T. L., Tate, W. L., and Petersen, K. J. (2016). Supplier role conflict: an investigation of its relational implications and impact on supplier accommodation. *Journal of Business Logistics* 37(2): 168-184.

Mysen, T., Svensson, G., and Högevold, N. (2012). Relationship quality—Relationship value and power balance in business relationships: Descriptives and propositions. *Journal of business-to-business marketing* 19(3): 248-285.

Nath, S. D., & Eweje, G. (2021). Inside the multi-tier supply firm: exploring responses to institutional pressures and challenges for sustainable supply management. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*.

Nguyen, A. (2020). The Individual Aspect of Interorganizational Cooperation: Favor-Based Cooperation. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 27(3): 221-245.

Ni, D., Li, K. W., and Tang, X. 2010. Social responsibility allocation in two-echelon supply chains: Insights from wholesale price contracts. *European Journal of Operational Research* 207(3): 1269-1279.

Nielsen, I. E., and Saha, S. (2018). Procurement planning in a multi-period supply chain: An epiphany. *Operations Research Perspectives* 5: 383-398.

Niu, B., and Xie, F. (2020). Incentive alignment of brand-owner and remanufacturer towards quality certification to refurbished products. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 242: 118314.

Ohmura, S., and Matsuo, H. (2016). The effect of risk aversion on distribution channel contracts: Implications for return policies. *International Journal of Production Economics* 176: 29-40.

Oosterhuis, M., Taco van, D. V., and Molleman, E. (2012). The value of upstream recognition of goals in supply chains. *Supply Chain Management* 17(6): 582-595

Palmatier, R. W., Sivadas, E., Stern, L. W., and El-Ansary, A. I. (2020), *Marketing Channel Strategy* 9th ed.

Panchal, G., Jain, V., Cheikhrouhou, N., and Gurtner, M. (2017). Equilibrium analysis in multi-echelon supply chain with multi-dimensional utilities of inertial players. *Journal of revenue and pricing management* 16(4): 417-436.

Panda, S. (2014). Coordination of a socially responsible supply chain using revenue sharing contracts. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 67: 92-104.

Panda, S., Modak, N. M., and Pradhan, D. (2016). Corporate social responsibility, channel coordination and profit division in a two-echelon supply chain. *International Journal of Management Science and Engineering Management* 11(1): 22-33.

Panda, S., Modak, N. M., Basu, M., and Goyal, S. K. (2015). Channel coordination and profit distribution in a socially responsible three-layer supply chain. *International Journal of Production Economics* 168: 224-233.

Panda, S., Modak, N. M., Sana, S. S., and Basu, M. (2015). Pricing and replenishment policies in dual-channel supply chain under continuous unit cost decrease. *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 256: 913-929.

Park, C., and Lee, H. (2015). Value co-creation processes—Early stages of value chains involving high-tech business markets: Samsung–qualcomm semiconductor foundry businesses. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 22(3): 229-252.

Pemer, F., and Skjølvik, T. (2016). Purchasing policy or purchasing police? The influence of institutional logics and power on responses to purchasing formalization. *Journal of Supply Chain Management* 52(4): 5-21.

Peres, I. F., and Kesan, J. P. (2015). The Role of Third-Party Institutions in Biomass Contracting: A Comparative Perspective. *Georgetown Environmental Law Review (GELR)* 28: 219.

Pereseina, V., Jensen, L. and Hertz, S. (2014). Challenges and conflicts in sustainable supply chain management: evidence from the heavy vehicle industry. *Supply Chain Forum: An International Journal* 15(1): 22-32.

Pittaway, L., Robertson, M., Munir, K., Denyer, D., and Neely, A. (2004). Networking and innovation: a systematic review of the evidence. *International journal of management reviews* 5(3-4): 137-168.

Pourmohammad-Zia, N., Karimi, B., & Rezaei, J. (2021). Food supply chain coordination for growing items: A trade-off between market coverage and cost-efficiency. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 242, 108289.

Prakash, C., Roy, V., & Charan, P. (2021). Mitigating interorganizational conflicts in humanitarian logistics collaboration: the roles of contractual agreements, trust and post-disaster environmental uncertainty phases. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*.

Pulles, N. J., and Loohuis, R. P. (2020). Managing buyer-supplier conflicts: the effect of buyer openness and directness on a supplier's willingness to adapt. *Journal of Supply Chain Management* 56(4): 65-81.

Qian, L., Yang, P., and Xue, J. (2018). Hindering or enabling structural social capital to enhance buyer performance? The role of relational social capital at two levels in China. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 25(3): 213-231.

Qin, J., Liu, X., and Pedrycz, W. (2017). An extended TODIM multi-criteria group decision making method for green supplier selection in interval type-2 fuzzy environment. *European Journal of Operational Research* 258 (2): 626-638.

Ramezani, M., Bashiri, M., and Tavakkoli-Moghaddam, R. (2013). A new multi-objective stochastic model for a forward/reverse logistic network design with responsiveness and quality level. *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 37(1/2):328-344.

Rasmussen, G. M. G., Jensen, P. L., and Gottlieb, S. C. (2017). Frames, agency and institutional change: the case of benchmarking in Danish construction. *Construction management and economics* 35(6): 305-323.

Rebehy, P. C. P. W., dos Santos Lima, S. A., Novi, J. C., and Salgado Jr, A. P. (2019). Reverse logistics systems in Brazil: Comparative study and interest of multistakeholders. *Journal of environmental management* 250: 109223.

Richards, D. W., & Safari, M. (2021). Disclosure effectiveness in the financial planning industry. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*.

Ryciuk, U. (2020). Supply Chain Governance Mechanisms: A Review and Typology. *Eurasian Business Perspectives*: 145-159.

Saha, S., Sarmah, S. P., and Modak, N. M. (2018). Single versus dual-channel: A strategic analysis in perspective of retailer's profitability under three-level dual-channel supply chain. *Asia Pacific Management Review* 23(2): 148-160.

Salonen, A., and Gabrielsson, M. (2012). The challenge of multinational corporation (MNC)-led growth and internationalization: The case of Nokia-dependent suppliers. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 19(2): 147-173.

Sanayei, A., Mousavi, S. F., and Yazdankhah, A. (2010). Group decision making process for supplier selection with VIKOR under fuzzy environment. *Expert Systems with Applications* 37(1): 24-30.

Seif, J., Yu, A. J., and Rahmannyay, F. (2018). Modelling and optimization of a bi-objective flow shop scheduling with diverse maintenance requirements. *International Journal of Production Research* 56(9): 3204-3225.

Selviaridis, K. and Norrman, A. (2014). Performance-based contracting in service supply chains: a service provider risk perspective. *Supply Chain Management* 19 (2): 153-172.

Shahzad, K., Ali, T., Kohtamäki, M. and Takala, J. (2020). Enabling roles of relationship governance mechanisms in the choice of inter-firm conflict resolution strategies. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing* 35(6): 957-969.

Shareef, M. A., Dwivedi, Y., Ahmed, J. U., Kumar, U., & Mahmud, R. (2021). Stakeholders conflict and private–public partnership chain (PPPC): supply chain of perishable product. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*.

Sharma, D. and Parida, B. (2018). Determinants of conflict in channel relationships: a meta-analytic review. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing* 33(7): 911-930.

Shen, J., & Qian, J. (2021). The impact of insufficient cash flow on payment term and supply chain contracts. *International Journal of Systems Science: Operations & Logistics*, 1-17.

Sherval, M., and Hardiman, K. (2014). Competing Perceptions of the Rural Idyll: responses to threats from coal seam gas development in Gloucester, NSW, Australia. *Australian Geographer* 45(2): 185-203.

Singh, A., & Trivedi, A. (2016). Sustainable green supply chain management: trends and current practices. *Competitiveness Review*.

Soosay, C. A., & Hyland, P. (2015). A decade of supply chain collaboration and directions for future research. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*.

Stern, L. W. (1971). The interorganizational management of distribution channels: prerequisites and perspectives, in G. Fisk (ed.) *New Essays in Marketing Theory*, Boston: Allen and Bacon, pp 301- 14

Steward, M. D., Wu, Z., and Hartley, J. L. (2010). Exploring supply managers' intrapreneurial ability and relationship quality. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 17(2): 127-148.

Suleiman, M. A., Huo, B., & Ye, Y. (2021). Linking supplier JIT to flexibility performance: the moderating impact of advanced manufacturing technology and human resource empowerment. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*.

Svanberg, M., Holm, H., & Cullinane, K. (2021). Assessing the impact of disruptive events on port performance and choice: the case of Gothenburg. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9(2), 145.

Svensson, G., Høgevoid, N., Ferro, C., Varela, J. C. S., Padin, C., and Wagner, B. (2016). A triple bottom line dominant logic for business sustainability: Framework and empirical findings. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 23(2): 153-188.

Taek Yi, H., Lee, J., and Dubinsky, A. J. (2010). An empirical investigation of relational conflicts in co-marketing alliances. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 17(3): 249-278.

Talay, C., Oxborrow, L., and Brindley, C. (2020). How small suppliers deal with the buyer power in asymmetric relationships within the sustainable fashion supply chain. *Journal of Business Research* 117: 604-614.

Tamannaie, M., Zarei, H., & Rasti-Barzoki, M. (2021). A game theoretic approach to sustainable freight transportation: Competition between road and intermodal road–rail systems with government intervention. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 153, 272-295.

Tang, L., Han, H., Tan, Z., & Jing, K. (2021). Centralized collaborative production scheduling with evaluation of a practical order-merging strategy. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1-20.

Tang, M., and Liao, H. (2021). A graph model for conflict resolution with inconsistent preferences among large-scale participants. *Fuzzy Optimization and Decision Making*: 1-24.

Tang, R., and Yang, L. (2020). Impacts of financing mechanism and power structure on supply chains under cap-and-trade regulation. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review* 139: 101957.

Tolmay, A. S. (2019). Antecedents of trust among buyer and seller within the South African automotive supply chains, *Journal of Transport and Supply Chain Management* 13(1): 1-11.

Tolmay, A.S. (2021) ‘Trust, commitment and business expansion in automotive supply chains in a developing country: a principal-agency perspective’, *Int. J. Applied Management Science*, Vol. 13, No. 1, pp.52–68

Tripathi, G., and Dave, K. (2013). Store format choice and relationship quality in apparel retail: A study of young and early middle-aged shoppers in New Delhi region. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 20(5): 479-487.

Tse, Y. K., Zhang, M., and Jia, F. (2018). The effects of risk and reward sharing on quality performance. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 38(12): 2367-2388

Vairaktarakis, G. L., and Aydinliyim, T. (2017). Benchmark schedules for subcontracted operations: decentralization inefficiencies that arise from competition and first-come-first-served processing. *Decision Sciences* 48(4): 657-690.

Vishnu, C. R., Das, S. P., Sridharan, R., Ram Kumar, P. N., and Narahari, N. S. (2020). Development of a reliable and flexible supply chain network design model: a genetic algorithm-based approach. *International Journal of Production Research*: 1-25.

Vlachokostas, C., Michailidou, A. V., & Achillas, C. (2021). Multi-criteria decision analysis towards promoting waste-to-energy management strategies: a critical review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 138, 110563.

Vos, F. G. S., Van der Lelij, R., Schiele, H., & Praas, N. H. J. (2021). Mediating the impact of power on supplier satisfaction: Do buyer status and relational conflict matter?. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 239, 108168.

Wang, C., Peng, Z., Yu, H., & Geng, S. (2021). Could the E-Commerce Platform’s Big Data Analytics Ease the Channel Conflict From Manufacturer Encroachment? An Analysis Based on Information Sharing and Risk Preference. *IEEE Access*, 9, 83552-83568.

Wang, J., Miao, H., and Yu, M. (2019). Interdependent order allocation in the two-echelon competitive and cooperative supply chain. *International Journal of Production Research* 57(4): 1190-1213.

Wang, R., and Song, J. (2011). Business marketing in China: Review and prospects. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing* 18(1): 1-49.

Wang, W. T., Wee, H. M., and Tsao, H. S. J. (2010). Revisiting the note on supply chain integration in vendor-managed inventory. *Decision Support Systems* 48(2): 419-420.

Wang, Z., and Liu, S. (2018). Supply chain coordination under trade credit and quantity discount with sales effort effects. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2018.

Wijen, F., and Chiroleu-Assouline, M. (2019). Controversy over voluntary environmental standards: A socioeconomic analysis of the Marine Stewardship Council. *Organization and Environment* 32(2): 98-124.

Xhoxhi, O., Pedersen, S. M., and Lind, K. M. (2018). How does the intermediaries’ power affect farmers-intermediaries’ trading relationship performance? *World Development Perspectives* 10: 44-50.

Xia, Z. J., Liu, Y., & Zhang, Q. (2021). A dual supply chain revenue sharing contract considering online reviews and rebate. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 1-11.

Xiao, D., Yang, Q., Sun, Q., & Fang, H. (2021). Vertical Channel Conflict Coordination Strategy of e-Commerce Supply Chain under Platform Brand Empowerment. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2021.

Xu, X., Meng, Z., and Shen, R. (2015). A cooperation model based on CVaR measure for a two-stage supply chain. *International Journal of Systems Science* 46(10): 1865-1873.

Yan, Q., & Ye, F. (2021). Manufacturer's channel selection in a capital-constrained supply chain under bargaining game. *RAIRO-Operations Research*, 55, S2161-S2179.

Yan, R. (2011). Managing channel coordination in a multi-channel manufacturer-retailer supply chain. *Industrial Marketing Management* 40(4): 636-642.

Yan, R., Pei, Z., and Myers, C. (2016). Do channel members value the multiple-cooperation strategy? *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services* 30: 84-95.

Yan, Y., Zhao, R., and Lan, Y. (2019). Moving sequence preference in coepetition outsourcing supply chain: Consensus or conflict. *International Journal of Production Economics* 208: 221-240.

Yang, C., Yang, R., Xu, T., and Li, Y. (2018). Negotiation model and tactics of manufacturing enterprise supply chain based on multi-agent. *Advances in Mechanical Engineering* 10(7): 1-8.

Yang, D. H., and Gao, X. (2017). Online retailer recommender systems: a competitive analysis. *International Journal of Production Research* 55(14): 4089-4109.

Yang, J., Zhang, X., Huang, Y., Su, J., Tsai, S. B., Chang, L. C., and Wang, J. (2019). Capacity Allocation and Compensation in a Dual-Channel Supply Chain under Uncertain Environment. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering* 2019.

Yang, L., Ji, J., Wang, M., and Wang, Z. (2018). The manufacturer's joint decisions of channel selections and carbon emission reductions under the cap-and-trade regulation. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 193: 506-523.

Yang, W., Si, Y., Zhang, J., Liu, S., & Appolloni, A. (2021). Coordination mechanism of dual-channel supply chains considering retailer innovation inputs. *Sustainability*, 13(2), 813.

Yarosan, E. V., Breen, L., Hou, J., & Sowter, J. (2021). Advancing the understanding of pharmaceutical supply chain resilience using complex adaptive system (CAS) theory. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*.

Yildiz, H., Yoon, J., Talluri, S., and Ho, W. (2016). Reliable supply chain network design. *Decision Sciences* 47(4): 661-698.

Yoo, S. H., & Cheong, T. (2021). Inventory model for sustainable operations of a closed-loop supply chain: Role of a third-party refurbisher. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 315, 127810.

Yoo, S. H., and Kim, B. C. (2016). Joint pricing of new and refurbished items: A comparison of closed-loop supply chain models. *International Journal of Production Economics* 182: 132-143.

Yu, J. P., and Pysarchik, D. T. (2018). Theoretical perspectives of supplier-buyer long-term relationships in India. *Journal of Business-to-business Marketing* 25(1): 31-50.

Yu, Y., Yang, Y., and Jing, F. (2017). The role of the third party in the trust repair process. *Journal of Business Research* 78: 233-241.

Zarei, H., Rasti-Barzoki, M., and Moon, I. (2020). A mechanism design approach to a buyer's optimal auditing policy to induce responsible sourcing in a supply chain. *Journal of environmental management* 254: 109721.

Zhang, L., and Wang, J. (2017). Coordination of the traditional and the online channels for a short-life-cycle product. *European Journal of Operational Research* 258 (2): 639-651.

Zhao, H. H., & Li, H. (2021). Decision analysis and coordination of supply chain with one brand retailer and two complete contract suppliers. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 1-13.

Zhao, L., You, J., & Fang, S. C. (2021). A dual-channel supply chain problem with resource-utilization penalty: Who can benefit from sales effort?. *Journal of Industrial & Management Optimization*, 17(5), 2837.

Zheng, C., Pang, Q., Li, T., Wang, G., Cai, Y., and Yang, L. (2019). The Farmers' Channel Selection and Sustainable Analysis under Carbon Tax Policy. *Sustainability* 11(10):765.

Zheng, S., & Yu, Y. (2021). Manufacturer encroachment with equal pricing strategy. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 152, 102346.

Zhou, W., Huang, W., and Zhang, R. (2014). A two-stage queueing network on form postponement supply chain with correlated demands. *Applied mathematical modelling* 38 (11/12): 2734-2743.

Zhou, Y. (2012). The research on a three-dimensional model for resolving supply chain conflict, from the perspective of organizational behavior. In *ICSSSM12* (pp. 210-214). IEEE.

Zu, Y. (2021). Inter-organizational contract control of advertising strategies in the supply chain. *Journal of Industrial & Management Optimization*.